

Industrial production of Spirulina as a protein source for bioactive peptide generation

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ABSTRACT

Background: Enzymatic hydrolysates containing peptides with biological activity are being studied as potential novel ingredients in functional foods, cosmetics, and pharmaceuticals. Recently, the microalga *Spirulina* was suggested as a potential source of bioactive peptides. However, the industrial production of bioactive peptides derived from *Spirulina* has not yet been achieved mainly caused by high production costs and a limited number of scientific reports with *in vivo* assessment of bioactivity.

Scope and approach: In this review, current challenges and needs for reducing the costs of *Spirulina* production are described. This study emphasises the importance of designing the process based on the end application of the produced biomass, focusing on those requirements needed to improve protein content. Moreover, current methods used to extract proteins and produce bioactive peptides are also summarised and described.

Key findings and conclusions: Large-scale production of *Spirulina* using raceway reactors is a reality. Different types of water and nutrients have been studied and their selection will depend largely on the end application of the produced biomass. The performance of large raceway reactors is unknown and more sophisticated systems such as thin-layer cascade reactors have not yet been assessed for the large scale production of *Spirulina*. *Spirulina* proteins are a promising source of bioactive peptides, although further *in vivo* studies are needed to validate the several bioactivities observed *in vitro*.

Keywords: *Arthrospira*, functional foods, nutraceuticals, bioactive compounds, cyanobacteria, proteins.

1. INTRODUCTION

Bioactive peptides are short sequences of amino acids that are present in foods or encrypted inside a larger protein but can exert biological activity once released. These peptides generally

contain 2-20 amino acids in length (although most of them are 2-4 amino acids long) and high abundance of hydrophobic amino acids (Chakrabarti et al., 2018). These molecules can be used as ingredients for the development of functional foods, nutraceuticals, and cosmetics (Aguilar-Toalá et al., 2019; Lorenzo et al., 2018) - products containing bioactive peptides are currently commercially available.

Bioactive peptides can be released either “naturally” during food processing (Toldrá et al., 2020) or gastrointestinal digestion (Gallego et al., 2020) or by enzymatic hydrolysis using commercial proteases from plant (Mazorra-Manzano et al., 2018) or microbial origin (Ryder et al., 2016) in controlled industrial facilities. The enzymatic production of bioactive peptides in industrial facilities has the advantage of allowing a complete control of the process. After hydrolysis, a large number of peptides are produced but only a limited number of peptides have bioactive properties and contribute to the bioactivity of the generated hydrolysate. For this reason, fractionation of the hydrolysate using molecular weight cut-off filtration (MWCO) is generally required. The use of complete hydrolysates or fractions containing peptides is desired for the majority of the applications, as purification of peptides is laborious and only economically viable for high-end applications such as pharmaceuticals. Most of the bioactive hydrolysates and peptides identified to date were obtained from milk and dairy products (Mudgil et al., 2018; Nielsen et al., 2017), meat and animal co-products (Ryder et al., 2016; Toldrá et al., 2020), fish and fish co-products (Ishak & Sarbon, 2018), and pulses (Awika & Duodu, 2017; Maleki & Razavi, 2020). Other sources such as algae (Lafarga et al., 2020) or cereals (Bleakley et al., 2017; Gong et al., 2020) have also been widely studied. Moreover, although a large number of different bioactivities have been attributed to bioactive peptides, the most commonly reported bioactivities are antioxidant, antimicrobial, and antihypertensive (Nielsen et al., 2017). Most of the bioactive peptides reported to date are available in the BIOPEP-UWM database, which is updated regularly and allows to not only search for bioactive sequences but also predict the potential bioactivity of a protein using *in silico* strategies, which

are very common in the literature as initial steps prior to *in vitro* and *in vivo* assessment (Minkiewicz et al., 2019).

As bioactive peptides are generated from proteins, and microalgae are protein-rich feedstocks, the potential utilisation of microalgae as a source for peptides has gained increased interest during the last decade. The most well-known and studied microalga is Spirulina, which is the commercial name given to describe mainly two species of cyanobacteria: *Arthrospira platensis* and *Arthrospira maxima* (Garrido-Cardenas et al., 2018). It is widely known for its extremely high protein content, which generally ranges within 50-60% (Lafarga, Fernández-Sevilla, et al., 2020) but has been reported to reach up to 70% on a dry weight basis when it is not limited by nitrogen (Danesi et al., 2002). Several Spirulina-derived peptides with either *in vitro* or *in vivo* biological activity have been described and are available in databases such as the above-described BIOPEP-UWM (Minkiewicz et al., 2019). These include the peptide IRDLDYI with an angiotensin-I-converting enzyme (ACE-I, EC 3.4.15.1) IC₅₀ value of 1.75 mM (Anekthanakul et al., 2019), the peptide HVLSRAPR that inhibited HT-29 cancer cells with an IC₅₀ value of 99.8 µg·L⁻¹ (Wang & Zhang, 2017), and the peptides LDAVNR and MMLDF which inhibit reactive oxygen species (ROS) production from mast and endothelial cells and exert potent anti-inflammatory effects (T.-S. Vo et al., 2013).

One of the main drawbacks of microalgae production is the high production cost of microalgal biomass, which renders the process only viable for certain high-end applications (Garrido-Cardenas et al., 2018). However, spirulina-based agricultural products such as biostimulants or biofertilisers, animal feeds (and aquafeeds), or human foods enriched in Spirulina are currently commercially available. This renders the implementation of Spirulina-derived peptides in cosmetics, nutraceuticals, and functional foods viable as these products are sold at higher prices. A key advantage of using Spirulina as a source of protein for bioactive peptide generation is that consumers consider this valuable raw material as safe, nutritious, and sustainable (Lafarga et al., 2021) in contrast to food co-products, which are unfamiliar to most consumers in developed countries and may be even regarded as unhealthy or waste (Mullen

et al., 2017). Microalgae are commercialised in the European Union (EU) under Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 known as novel foods regulation. It defines a Novel Food as food that had not been consumed to a significant degree by humans in the EU before 15 May 1997 and ensures that foods introduced into the European market are safe for consumers and are properly labelled. Because of its long history of consumption, Spirulina and proteins derived from Spirulina can be commercialised in the EU as food without need to comply with Regulation (EU) 2015/2283 – Spirulina is available in the Novel Food Catalogue available at https://ec.europa.eu/food/food/novel-food/novel-food-catalogue_en. Spirulina is also considered as Generally Recognised as Safe (GRAS) by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) of the US and is the most widely consumed microalga in the EU and the US (Boukid & Castellari, 2021).

The aim of this review paper was to summarise current Spirulina production processes as well as the most common strategies followed to enhance the protein content of the biomass and maximise protein recoveries focusing on those that could be implemented in large-scale industrial facilities. Moreover, the current manuscript also lists some of the most recent biologically active peptides derived from Spirulina and their potential use in the food industry.

2. Production of *Spirulina*

Because of their small size, microalgae cannot be harvested from the environment and must be produced inland in controlled industrial facilities – recently, offshore production of microalgae has been studied (Novoveská et al., 2016). Spirulina is not a eukaryotic microalga but a prokaryotic cyanobacteria (Bacteria, Cyanobacteria, Cyanophyceae, Oscillatoriales, Microcoleaceae, *Arthrospira*). However, in the current review (and in most of the scientific literature) both are included into the term “microalgae” as both are photosynthetic microorganisms and are produced similarly. Main steps of microalgae production include (i)

the design of the photobioreactor, (ii) the selection and optimisation of the culture media and culture conditions, and (iii) harvesting and drying of the biomass are described below.

2.1 Large-scale production of microalgae

Besides selecting a robust and highly productive strain capable to grow under a wide range of environmental conditions, (i) the selection of a photobioreactor capable of providing the optimal conditions required by the selected strain, and (ii) the possibility to adjust the production system because of the (inevitably) changing environmental outdoor conditions are key aspects that need to be considered when producing microalgae (Acién et al., 2012). Photobioreactors must be designed to allow the control, in the best possible way, of the above-discussed parameters that influence biomass productivity: pH, temperature, and light availability (and others, such as dissolved oxygen concentration, mass transfer, etc.). Providing optimal conditions inside the lab is easy but turns a very complex challenge when the process is up-scaled and carried out outdoors.

Microalgae are mass produced using photobioreactors, which can be divided into two main groups: open and closed systems (Figure 1). Several different photobioreactor designs are available in the literature. However, only a few have been up-scaled and validated outdoors (Lafarga, 2019a). The current review will only discuss raceways and tubular reactors, which are the most common and widespread designs, and thin-layer cascade reactors which are highly productive and one of the top trends in microalgae biotechnology. Raceway designs are open ponds divided into two or four channels where the culture is recirculated, most of the times using a paddlewheel – although propellers have also been evaluated and demonstrated potential for industrial implementation (Chiaromonti et al., 2013). The mixing section of raceways include a sump, used to bubble gases and supply CO₂ while removing dissolved oxygen (toxic for microalgae above a specie-dependent threshold). The length of the channels is proportional to their width. Length/width ratios of 10-20 are accepted, which allow to reduce head losses into the channel (Acién et al., 2017). Their surface-to-volume ratios are low (approximately 5-10 m⁻¹) and their areal productivity in the range 20-25 g·m⁻²·day⁻¹. Culture

depths in raceways vary between 0.20-0.40 m. The higher the culture depth, the lower the light penetration inside the culture; for this reason, lower culture depths (0.10-0.15 m) have also been investigated (Morillas-España et al., 2020). Overall, the culture depth has to be optimised for each reactor (and season) to maximise agitation, mass transfer, and light availability. The most common liquid velocity in raceway designs is $0.2 \text{ m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, as it avoids cells to settle at the bottom of the reactor. As they are open to the environment, raceways have a high risk of contamination with other microorganisms including microalgal strains. However, because of the high bicarbonate content of the media used for *Spirulina* production, the risk of contamination is lower. Indeed, raceways are the most common design for mass production of *Spirulina*.

Tubular photobioreactors are the most common closed system at large-scale. They consist of glass or plastic tubes that are used to recirculate the culture using pumps or air streams. Their surface-to-volume ratio is around 80 m^{-1} , allowing to achieve much higher biomass concentrations and productivities (Ación et al., 2017). Their main advantage is that as these systems are closed, they allow a complete control of the process. Their cost is also higher and for this reason they are used for producing biomass for high-value applications or for the production of sensible strains that cannot be produced in open systems because of contamination with other microalgal strains or microorganisms. Moreover, agitation in tubular reactors is achieved by using pumps, and some microalgal strains such as *Spirulina* are sensitive to the shear stress caused by pumps causing decreased growth rate and cell viability (Wang & Lan, 2018). The last photobioreactor design that will be discussed in the current paper are thin-layer cascade reactors, which are currently being up-scaled and validated in several locations. These are open systems with two unique characteristics: their low culture depth and the recirculation of the culture that is provided by a slope of 0.1-2.0%. Culture depths range from 0.5 to 5.0 cm, which allow to maximise light utilisation, and their surface-to-volume ratio is within the range $25\text{-}50 \text{ m}^{-1}$ enabling high areal productivities, which can be higher than $40 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (Morales-Amaral et al., 2015). Up to the best of the authors'

knowledge, only one publication assessed the performance of thin-layer cascade reactors when used to produce *Spirulina*. In that study, the authors used a 6 L thin-layer cascade reactor and reported a lower content of pigments and a higher biomass productivity ($20 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$) when compared to an open pond (Silva Benavides et al., 2017). Further studies using larger thin-layer cascade reactors are needed and ongoing.

Most of the data available in the literature has been obtained using small (0.5-5.0 L) photobioreactors indoors with artificial illumination. Some studies were performed outdoors, with sunlight as the source of light and energy, but again most of them using small reactors or operating in batch mode (Table 1). The problem with small reactors is that theoretical biomass productivities obtained using small and controlled reactors are not comparable to those obtained in large industrial facilities, while the drawback of operating in batch mode is that semi continuous cultivation results in 3- to 4-fold increase in areal productivity (Yadav et al., 2020) and is preferred for industrial processes. Up to the best of the authors' knowledge, there is only one report of *Spirulina* production using pilot-scale reactors operated in semi continuous mode for one complete year. It was conducted from 2005 to 2006 in Brazil using raceway reactors (37.1 m^2 , 10 m^3) and reported an average biomass productivity of $21.6 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}\cdot\text{day}^{-1}$ (Morais et al., 2009). Further studies outdoors using large photobioreactors are needed to assess the real outdoor productivity of *Spirulina*, ideally using photobioreactors larger than 100 m^2 – which is challenging for research groups in universities and research institutes.

2.2 Culture media and environmental conditions

Spirulina is native from Lake Texcoco in America and Lake Chad in Africa where it grows naturally and is collected for human consumption. *A. platensis* and *A. maxima* are present in freshwater bodies characterise by high levels of carbonate and bicarbonate and high pH values. Commercial production of *Spirulina* occurs in open ponds that mimic optimal conditions of saline alkaline lakes. Zarrouks' medium developed in 1966 has been used as the standard medium for *Spirulina* production for many years. This medium requires the utilisation of expensive chemicals and high quantities of sodium bicarbonate, which is not

advantageous for large-scale production. For this reason, during the last decades, several research groups developed *Spirulina* growth media using readily available and cheaper nutrient sources including commercial fertilisers (Gómez et al., 2020; Madkour et al., 2012; Raouf et al., 2006), food co-products (Barrocal et al., 2010; Coca et al., 2015), wastewater (Chang et al., 2013; Phang et al., 2000; Zhai et al., 2017), and seawater (Leema et al., 2010). For large-scale production, the utilisation of low cost chemicals as the nutrient source is mandatory to render the process viable. However, the selection of the nutrient source will partially depend on the end application of the produced biomass as, for example, microalgae produced using wastewater cannot be incorporated into foods. Modifications of Zarrouks' medium were also reported, for example, using cheaper nitrogen sources like $(\text{NH}_4)_2\text{SO}_4$ and NaNO_3 (Rodrigues et al., 2011) or NH_4Cl (Carvalho et al., 2004). Different modifications of Zarrouks' medium as well as the outcomes of producing *Spirulina* using alternative nutrient sources were revised recently (Ragaza et al., 2020).

Besides the availability of inorganic nutrients, the pH value of the media is a critical factor for producing microalgae. The concentration of CO_2 in the atmosphere is not high enough to achieve concentrated microalgal cultures and microalgae production requires an additional CO_2 input into the process. The most common strategy is the direct injection of CO_2 , air enriched in CO_2 , or flue gases rich in CO_2 , which is also used as a strategy to control the pH of the culture. However, *Spirulina* is known for exclusive and preferential uptake of bicarbonate. After conversion to carbon dioxide and carbonate, the former is used as the carbon source and the latter released into the medium (Ragaza et al., 2020). The optimum pH value for *Spirulina* growth is around 9.0-10.0, where bicarbonate prevails in the bicarbonate/carbonate equilibrium (Ragaza et al., 2020). Temperature is also key to increase biomass and protein productivity. Indeed, in a recent study it was demonstrated that higher biomass densities and productivities were achieved when *A. platensis* was produced at temperature ranging between 30 and 35 °C (Colla et al., 2007). Results were consistent with those reported in another study, where optimum biomass productivities were achieved at 30

°C and pH 9.0 (Ogbonda et al., 2007). Heating microalgal cultures is currently not economically viable, and for this reason selecting a suitable location for the photobioreactor is of key importance. Some reports suggested that modifying the culture depth could be used as a strategy to control temperature in photobioreactors (Rodríguez-Miranda et al., 2021), although temperature control is not an easy task.

Light availability is the most important parameter when producing any photosynthetic organism. Artificial illumination is an option but the use of sunlight is preferred. One of the drawbacks of microalgae production is known as the shadow or self-shading effect of microalgae, which plays an important role in the dynamics of microalgae growth. Large-scale microalgae production is conducted outdoors, where cultures are subjected to environmental conditions, namely solar radiation and temperature that (unfortunately) cannot be controlled. However, different strategies can be followed to maximise biomass production and avoid self-shading and extreme temperatures in microalgal cultures. In the present review, we will only discuss the two main operational conditions that can be easily adjusted to maximise biomass productivity: culture depth and dilution rate. As highlighted before, modifying the culture depth can be used as a strategy to regulate the temperature of the culture (Rodríguez-Miranda et al., 2021) and selecting a suitable location for the bioreactor is crucial to achieve commercial success. For example, in the south of Spain, microalgal cultures can reach up to 40 °C in summer (Morillas-España et al., 2020), which is lethal to certain microalgal strains. In the case of *Spirulina*, temperatures over 35 °C were negatively correlated with microalgal growth (Colla et al., 2007) and therefore, in hot regions/seasons, it is desirable to operate using high culture depths that minimise the overheating of the culture. The culture depth of the culture is also related to other important parameters rather than temperature, which demonstrates the complexity of microalgae production and the need for a robust production strategy that can adapt depending on environmental fluctuations. The culture depth can also be modified (in this case, reduced) to increase light availability inside the culture. Indeed, thin-layer cascade photobioreactors that will be discussed in the following section are highly productive because

of a much higher light availability when compared to raceway designs (Morillas-España et al., 2020). Finally, the dilution rate imposed to the system is key to maximise biomass productivity. The dilution rate is the amount of culture that is daily harvested and replaced with fresh culture medium. Optimising the dilution rate allows to reduce the biomass concentration of the culture and therefore maximise nutrient and light availability and could also be used as a strategy to control temperature in large open ponds. The optimum dilution rate for producing microalgae will depend on a large number of factors such as photobioreactor design, location of the reactor, environmental conditions, microalgal strain being produced, composition of the culture media, among others. The optimum value for raceway reactors is generally within 0.2-0.3 day⁻¹, although this needs to be calculated for every process independently.

2.3 Harvesting and drying

In addition to selecting the optimum culture media, locating the photobioreactor in the correct place, and designing the reactor to provide the microalga with the optimal conditions, harvesting and drying of the biomass are also main factors determining the success of microalgae production and are key to the quality of the produced biomass. Both processes account for approximately 30% of the overall production cost (Garrido-Cardenas et al., 2018). The most common strategy used for microalgal biomass harvesting is centrifugation. Main reasons include its ease of use and scale-up and high capture efficiencies, higher than 90% (Dassey & Theegala, 2013). However, the use of centrifuges alone for algal separation is very energy intensive (Pienkos & Darzins, 2009). A two-step strategy including an initial pre-concentration step by sedimentation or flotation followed by a second dewatering step by centrifugation has been suggested as a strategy to reduce costs. However, because of the large size of *Spirulina*, when compared to other microalgae and cyanobacteria, biomass harvesting is simplified. Flotation alone was suggested as a good strategy to recover the biomass of *Spirulina*, as previous reports demonstrated that approximately 80% of *A. platensis* cells can be harvested by flotation when the culture is left in a static condition for 2 h (Kim et al., 2005). Authors of that study also suggested that addition of NaCl could enhance the

flotation activity of *A. platensis* (Kim et al., 2005). Moreover, Spirulina harvesting by filtration is common. The efficiency of this strategy is highly influenced by the concentration of the culture. Indeed, after 30 min of filtration of *A. maxima* at a concentration of 40 g·L⁻¹ led to a flux reduction of 86%, which was higher than the 63% reduction observed at a concentration of 10 g·L⁻¹ (Kanchanatip et al., 2016). Membrane fouling is a major drawback in membrane-based microalgae harvesting but, recently, a novel tilted panel system significantly improved fouling control while harvesting Spirulina and reached a high plateau permeability of 540 L·m⁻²·h⁻¹·bar⁻¹ (Ismail et al., 2021). This permeability value was achieved using an aeration rate of 1 L·min⁻¹ and an energy input of 0.2 kWh·m⁻³ (Ismail et al., 2021). The utilisation of membrane technologies in microalgae production is promising as this strategy could reduce production costs (energy consumption) while simultaneously increase the sustainability of the process by reducing water requirements.

Drying is the most expensive step of Spirulina production. The method used for drying Spirulina depends on several factors such as the end use of the produced biomass (quality) or the production scale. While spray drying is the most common strategy used for large producers, small Spirulina producers generally dry the produced biomass using convective drying processes. Other strategies such as solar drying or freeze-drying have been evaluated but are not as relevant because of the high risk of contamination and low quality of the biomass when dried using the former and the high production costs of the latter. When used as a feedstock for protein isolation, one advantage is that the biomass does not need to be dried before protein extraction therefore reducing production costs and simplifying the process.

3. Protein extraction and bioactive peptide generation

3.1. Protein extraction

Despite the high protein content of Spirulina, if used to produce bioactive peptides and hydrolysates, Spirulina proteins should be first extracted to facilitate proteolysis and increase

the purity of the end products. The need for a cell wall disruption step when producing microalgae based products is generally mandatory because of the strong cell wall of most microalgal strains. Not only for extracting valuable microalgal products but even when used as food, a disruption step improves the bioaccessibility of nutrients and bioactive compounds contained within microalgal biomass (Bernaerts et al., 2020). In the case of *Spirulina*, its cell wall is divided into four layers (L-I to L-IV). Layers L-I and L-III are formed of fibrillary molecules, being L-I a β -1,2-glucan layer (Chen et al., 2020). L-II is a peptidoglycan layer while L-IV is a membrane covered with acidic polysaccharides (Chen et al., 2020). Several strategies have been studied as cell wall disruption pre-treatments to increase recovery yields of proteins and other compounds. These include high pressure homogenisation (Elain et al., 2020), sonication (Vernès et al., 2019), ohmic heating (Ferreira-Santos et al., 2020), pulsed electric fields (Käferböck et al., 2020), bead milling (Balti et al., 2021), among others.

The most common strategy to recover *Spirulina* proteins is isoelectric solubilisation/precipitation. Isoelectric solubilisation/precipitation consists of solubilising the maximum amount of protein possible by increasing the pH of the solution and precipitation the maximum amount of protein possible by adjusting the pH to the pI of the protein. This strategy has been used to recover proteins from varied food sources. As different proteins have different pH values, the selected pI should be the one that allows the precipitation of the largest amount of proteins. Different reports aimed at optimising the recovery of proteins from *Spirulina*. For example, a recent report utilised a surface response methodology to optimise the precipitation of proteins and concluded that the optimum conditions to recover proteins from *Spirulina* were sonication and solubilisation at alkaline conditions followed by precipitation at pH 3.9 (Sánchez-Zurano et al., 2020). This value is in line with other reports that suggested that the isoelectric point of *Spirulina* proteins varies within 3 and 4 (Benelhadj et al., 2016; Parimi et al., 2015; Yüçetepe et al., 2019). The precipitated proteins can be recovered by centrifugation or by using membrane technologies. Because of the high content of salts in the culture media and the acids and bases used to adjust the solutions pH, a clean-

up step is recommended. Dialysis and ultrafiltration can efficiently increase the purity of proteins by removing salts and can be easily implemented at large-scale. Other strategies such as chromatographic techniques can be used to isolate specific high-value proteins such as c-phycoerythrin (Niu et al., 2007) – Figure 2. Phycobiliproteins such as phycoerythrin are especially attractive because they can be used in food as pigments (Martelli et al., 2014) and as functional ingredients with potential for being used in the treatment of chronic kidney disease (Memije-Lazaro et al., 2018). Purified phycobiliproteins were also used as sources for bioactive peptides with *in vitro* antidiabetic properties (Li et al., 2020).

3.2. *In vitro* and *in vivo* bioactivity of Spirulina derived peptides

As mentioned previously, bioactive peptides are encrypted within the sequence of their parent protein and need to be released and reach the target site in sufficient quantities to exert their biological activity. Although peptides can be released during food processing (Toldrá et al., 2020) or during gastrointestinal digestion (Gallego et al., 2020), their production is not controlled and the quantity of peptides released could be too low to exert a beneficial health effect. Therefore, the current manuscript will only discuss the production of biologically active peptides using commercial proteases. This is the most common strategy because of the high specificity of proteases and the possibility to control the process. Enzymes used for hydrolysing proteins are generally derived from animals, microorganisms or plants.

In silico strategies have been widely used during the last decade to identify proteins and peptides with biological activity. These can be used to predict protein cleavage by a given enzyme, thus allowing to select the most promising proteins and enzymes for bioactive peptide generation. Other tools allow to predict the toxicity of a peptide (Gupta et al., 2013) and even the antimicrobial (Mooney et al., 2012) or ACE-I inhibitory activity (Kumar et al., 2015) of peptides. The identification of a potential peptide or bioactivity *in silico* can be used to reduce costs and save time, but it is just the first step of bioactive peptide production. It is important to highlight that to consider a peptide or any other compound as bioactive, the health promoting activity of the peptide must be validated *in vivo*. Some of the most recently reported

bioactive peptides derived from *Spirulina* are shown in Table 2. The most commonly studied strain was *A. platensis*. Most common enzymes used were gastrointestinal enzymes, namely pepsin (EC 3.4.23.1), trypsin (EC 3.4.21.4), and chymotrypsin (EC 3.4.21.1) although other enzymes such as papain (EC 3.4.22.2) and Alcalase (commercial mixture of proteases) have been evaluated. The general procedure for peptide purification and identification was in most cases an initial purification step based on molecular weight cut-off (MWCO) filtration using 1-10 kDa membranes followed by one or two chromatographic steps and identification by mass spectrometry. Most of the studies assessed bioactivity *in vitro*, although antihypertensive and anticarcinogenic activity of peptides and hydrolysates derived from *Spirulina* have been reported in animal models. The most common bioactivities studied to date include inhibition of ACE-I and dipeptidyl peptidase-IV (DPP-IV; EC 3.4.14.5) which are related to hypertension and diabetes respectively. The peptides IQP and VEP, with demonstrated *in vitro* and *in vivo* antihypertensive activity were also considered in a different study where they were absorbed intact through human intestinal Caco-2 monolayers (He et al., 2018), which supports their biological activity. Anticarcinogenic, antiatherosclerotic, antioxidative, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial peptides were also produced by enzymatic hydrolysis of *Spirulina* proteins. Interestingly, *Spirulina* has been recently used for the identification of a large number of peptides with potential antiallergenic properties, which should be further investigated because of the increased prevalence of asthma and allergic disease during the last decades (Vo et al., 2014; Vo et al., 2018).

Bioactive peptides and other bioactive compounds derived from *Spirulina* have potential to achieve a health claim and for being commercialised as therapeutic products. A Health Claim is defined as any statement made about the relationship between food and health. The European Commission (EC) authorises different health claims provided they are based on substantial scientific evidence and can be easily understood by consumers. Only a limited number of claims are currently accepted and these are listed in Commission Regulation (EU) 432/2012. It is accepted that α -linolenic acid contributes to the maintenance of normal blood

cholesterol levels and that docosahexaenoic acid contributes to maintenance of normal brain function. Anticarcinogenic properties, for example, are not accepted health claims according to European regulations. The Commissions' implementing rules are established in Regulation (EC) 353/2008 and include human studies addressing the specific relationship between the food or food ingredient and the claimed effect. As mentioned before, only a limited number of reports demonstrated the *in vivo* bioactivity of peptides and hydrolysates derived from food sources and most of these were carried out using animal models. The lack of human intervention studies remains as one of the main challenges of bioactive peptide production and commercialisation. For example, several *in vitro* and animal studies suggested the potential of Spirulina to promote glycaemic health. However, the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) could not identify an effect between Spirulina and normal blood glucose concentrations in the general population because the evidence provided was obtained from *in vitro* trials, which is not enough to achieve a Health Claim under EU regulations (EFSA, 2010). The therapeutic application of bioactive peptides derived from Spirulina is challenging. The tripeptides IPP and VPP are being used to manufacture functional foods with antihypertensive activity in Japan and other countries but despite more than 15 human intervention studies, the EFSA could not establish a cause and effect relationship between the consumption of these peptides and normal blood pressure (EFSA, 2012). However, products with potential health benefits based on bioactive peptides and hydrolysates are already being commercialised in several countries including the US, New Zealand, Japan, and China (Chalamaiah et al., 2019). These include Seacure[®] (Proper Nutrition Inc, US) which promotes wound healing and supports the immune system, PeptAldie[™] (BASF, Germany) which helps to modulate inflammation, and Capolac[®] (Arla Food Ingredients, Denmark) which promotes calcium absorption. Animal trials and human intervention studies demonstrating the health benefits of consuming Spirulina and Spirulina-derived peptides and hydrolysates will boost the use of these ingredients in the food and functional food industries.

Conclusions

The large-scale commercial production of Spirulina is a reality, although several attempts are being made to reduce production costs. Novel culture media formulated using low cost chemicals and membrane technologies to reduce energy requirements are some of the most widely studied strategies. Moreover, further long-term studies using large photobioreactors are needed as production using large reactors is carried out by private companies and the performance of these large systems is unknown. Spirulina is rich in protein, which needs to be extracted prior to enzymatic hydrolysis generally by isoelectric solubilisation/precipitation. A cell wall disruption step is needed as a pre-treatment because the strong cell wall of Spirulina limits protein extraction. The use of Spirulina as a source of peptides is a relatively new research topic and, therefore, further studies are needed to identify a larger number of peptides and to assess the observed bioactivities *in vivo*. Studies are ongoing, but results reported to date suggested that Spirulina proteins have a huge potential for being used as feedstock for the production of bioactive hydrolysates and peptides with potential use in the development of functional foods.

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The authors declare no competing financial interest.

Credit authorship contribution statement

Tomas Lafarga: Conceptualisation, Writing – Original draft, Funding acquisition; **Ana Sánchez-Zurano:** Conceptualisation, Writing – Original draft; **Silvia Villaró:** Conceptualisation, Writing – Original draft; **Ainoa Morillas-España:** Conceptualisation, Writing – Original draft; **Gabriel Acién:** Conceptualisation, Writing – Original draft.

Figure legends

Figure 1. Open and closed photobioreactors at the University of Almería in Spain.

Figure 2. Spirulina: Proteinaceous ingredients for the food and functional food industries

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

1 **Table 1. Spirulina production: Culture medium, photobioreactor design, production mode, and biomass productivity.**

Strain used	Culture medium	Production system(s) and mode of operation	Biomass productivity (biomass concentration)	Other information	Reference
<i>Arthrospira</i> sp. LEB18	Aquaculture effluents supplemented with 25% of Zarrouk nutrients	A. Indoor photobioreactor, 1 L, batch mode B. Outdoor raceway, 5 L, batch mode	A. 0.20 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (2.32 g·L ⁻¹) B. 0.26 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (3.33 g·L ⁻¹)	Major fatty acids detected were 40.1% palmitic (C16:0) and 26.1% α-linolenic acid (C18:3n3). High removal of nutrients.	(Cardoso et al., 2020)
<i>Arthrospira</i> sp. LEB18	Zarrouk medium	Outdoor raceway, 250 L, batch mode. Two locations studied.	0.02 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (1.0 g·L ⁻¹)	Extracellular polymeric substances were abundant and composed of polysaccharides and proteins with biotechnological potential.	(de Jesus et al., 2019)
<i>Arthrospira</i> sp. LEB18	Zarrouk medium	Outdoor raceway, 240 L, batch mode. Two locations studied.	0.01-0.05 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (0.8-1.5 g·L ⁻¹)	The protein content of the biomass was around 60%. Biomass was considered as safe for food applications and had a high content of phycocyanin and volatile compounds.	(de Jesus et al., 2018)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Zarrouk medium	Outdoor raceway, 1400 L, batch mode	0.072 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (1.1 g·L ⁻¹)	Optimum CO ₂ fixation rate, protein, and phycocyanin content were 0.13 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ , 64%, and 14% respectively.	(Mehar et al., 2019)
<i>Arthrospira</i> sp	Industrial wastewater	A. Indoor customised photobioreactor, 50 L, batch mode B. Outdoor customised photobioreactor, 500 L, batch mode	A. 0.11 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (8.1 g·L ⁻¹) B. 0.09 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (7.5 g·L ⁻¹)	High nutrient recoveries.	(Krishnamoorthy et al., 2019)

<i>A. platensis</i>	Guillard's f/2 culture medium	A. Indoor Fibonacci-type photobioreactor, 6 L, batch mode 2. Outdoor Fibonacci-type photobioreactor, 250 L, batch mode	1. 0.30 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (1.9 g·L ⁻¹) 2. 1.1 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (5.0 g·L ⁻¹)	The photobioreactor was design following the Fibonacci equation that allowed a 1.4-fold higher availability of light.	(Díaz et al., 2019)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Modified Zarrouk medium	10 m ² biofilm system with multiple vertical surfaces	38.3 g·m ⁻² ·day ⁻¹ (NR)	Protein content over 60% and overall CO ₂ usage efficiency of 75%.	(Wang et al., 2019)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Zarrouk medium	Outdoor thin-layer cascade reactor, 60 L, batch mode	38.3 g·m ⁻² ·day ⁻¹ (NR)	Higher biomass productivity but lower phycocyanin content in the thin-layer cascade reactor than in the control (open pond).	(Silva Benavides et al., 2017)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Medium formulated using natural sodium bicarbonate and commercial chemicals.	Outdoor raceway, 30 m ³ , semi-continuous mode.	1. 25-35 g·m ⁻² ·day ⁻¹ (0.2-0.6 g·L ⁻¹)	Microbiological contaminants were identified as bacteria and microzooplanktons.	(Yu et al., 2019)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Zarrouk medium	Indoor photobioreactors, 0.35 L, semi-continuous mode	0.18-0.25 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (1.3-1.6 g·L ⁻¹)	Higher productivities at 20-35 °C. Prolonged exposure at 35 °C led to pigment degradation.	(Karemore et al., 2020)
<i>Arthrospira</i> sp. LEB 18	Seawater supplemented to mimic Zarrouk medium	Indoor bubble column, 1.8 L, batch mode	0.14-0.18 g·L ⁻¹ ·day ⁻¹ (2.2-2.3 g·L ⁻¹)	Spirulina can be produced using seawater. Production using seawater led to increased carbohydrate productivity.	(Bezerra et al., 2020)

2 Abbreviations: NR, not reported.

3 **Table 2. Spirulina-derived bioactive peptides and hydrolysates**

Strain used	Bioactive peptide generation	Purification and determination methods	Peptide sequence	Bioactivity assessed	Reference
<i>A. platensis</i>	Alcalase (E/S 0.04%, 50 °C, pH 8.5, 10h)	SEC followed by RP-HPLC and MALDI-TOF-MS	IQP	<i>In vitro</i> : ACE-I Inhibition (IC ₅₀ 5.7 μM) <i>In vivo</i> : 10 mg·kg ⁻¹ reduced SBP and DBP in SHRs at 4, 6, and 8 h after administration	(Lu et al., 2010)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Papain (5 U of enzyme in 30 mL of 2% substrate solution, 90 °C, pH 7.0, 9 h)	MWCO filtration (1 and 5 kDa)	IQP and VEP	<i>In vivo</i> : antihypertensive activity in SHRs	(Pan et al., 2015)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Peptides produced during ultrasound-assisted protein extraction	LC-ESI-MS/MS	LRSELAAWSR	<i>In vitro</i> : α-amylase (IC ₅₀ 313 μg·mL ⁻¹), α-glucosidase (IC ₅₀ 134 μg·mL ⁻¹ μM), and DPP-IV inhibition (IC ₅₀ 167 μg·mL ⁻¹)	(Hu et al., 2019)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Pepsin (E/S 6%, 37 °C, pH 2, 10 h)	MWCO filtration (3 and 10 kDa)	EYFDALA	<i>In vitro</i> : Higher radical scavenging activity than vitamin C and attenuated free radical-	(Zeng et al., 2020)

		and MALDI-TOF-MS		induced oxidative hemolysis, inhibited MDA formation, and promoted the protection of erythrocytes	
<i>A. platensis</i>	Alkaline protease (4300 U, 55 °C, pH 7, 3 h) followed by papain (E/S 4.5%, 60 °C, pH 6.5, 3.5 h)	SEC followed by LC-ESI-MS/MS	KLVDASHRLATGDVAVRA	<i>In vitro</i> : Antimicrobial effect on <i>E. coli</i> (MIC 8 mg·mL ⁻¹) and <i>S. aureus</i> (MIC 16 mg·mL ⁻¹).	(Sun et al., 2016)
<i>A. platensis</i>	Trypsin (E/S 2% for each enzyme, 37 °C, pH 8, 16 h) and pepsin (E/S 2% for each enzyme, 37 °C, pH 2-3, 16 h)	MWCO filtration (3 kDa) followed by LC-ESI-MS/MS	Whole hydrolysate (55-76 peptides identified)	<i>In vitro</i> : DPP-IV inhibition (IC ₅₀ 0.1-3.4 mg·mL ⁻¹) and ACE-I inhibition (IC ₅₀ 0.28-3.0 mg·mL ⁻¹)	(Aiello et al., 2019)

4 Abbreviations: ACE-I, angiotensin-I-converting enzyme; E/S, enzyme-to-substrate ration; ESI, electrospray ionisation; DPP-IV, dipeptidyl peptidase-IV; HPLC,
5 high performance liquid chromatography; LC, liquid chromatography; MALDI, matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization; MDA, malondialdehyde; MIC, minimum
6 inhibitory concentration MS, mass spectrometry; MWCO, molecular weight cut-off; RP, reversed-phase; SEC, size exclusion chromatography; SHRs,
7 spontaneously hypertensive rats; TOF, time-of-flight;

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